

THE PROBLEMS OF APPLYING THE VIEWS OF EASTERN THINKERS IN THE FORMATION OF IDEAS OF HUMANITY AND GOODNESS IN CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE

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Abstract. *Humanitarianism is a concept that expresses concern for the creation of conditions for the manifestation of human dignity and dignity, freedom and dignity, happiness and equal rights, in general, all the principles of humanity. Caring about human destiny, people's interests, country's development is the main goal of humanitarianism.*

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In our country, in the conditions of the coronavirus pandemic, regular attention was paid to protecting the health and safety of the population, finding solutions to their problems and resolving their shortcomings. In such trying days, the humanitarian character of our compatriots, who are distinguished by their high human qualities and generosity - material and spiritual encouragement - gave us the confidence to overcome this disease as soon as possible. The importance of humanitarianism to the state policy is also very visible. For example, the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in cooperation with the United Nations Children's Fund - UNICEF representative office in Uzbekistan, in cooperation with Mercy Homes and

Humanitarian aid is being sent to children's towns, specialized boarding schools for children with developmental disabilities, social and legal assistance centers for minors under the Ministry of Internal Affairs. At this point, we will briefly touch on some facts and figures related to the humanitarian activities of this year.

According to the order of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, humanitarian aid was delivered to India on May 1. These humanitarian shipments mainly consist of mobile oxygen concentrator kits, various medical supplies that are in high demand.

In turn, the state and people of Turkey provided humanitarian aid to the people of Syrdarya who were affected by the flood in 2020. This year's humanitarian aid consisted of 4,000 sets of blankets, pillows and pillowcases. Based on the measures developed by the regional government, humanitarian aid was distributed to flood victims and families in need of help. In this place, several groups from our country helped to rescue people from the houses damaged by the earthquakes in Turkey this year, and they saw a lot of people. Aid packages were delivered to Turkey by our generous people. The principle of mutual philanthropy between these countries is the relations of goodness repeated throughout history, and the ideas of philanthropy and goodness have been developed in the eastern countries since time immemorial.

One of the leading, main components of high spirituality is humanitarianism. Therefore, they approach and interpret the concept of humanitarianism from different angles. In our opinion, philanthropy means that a person values his motherland and spares no effort for his people and

loved ones. Although this definition does not cover all aspects of humanitarianism, the definition is correctly understood if the word "esteem of Islam" is approached in a broad sense.

For a broader understanding of the concept of humanitarianism, it is necessary to thoroughly study the works of Furqat, Fitrat, Abdulla Kadiri, Cholpon, Abdulla Avloni, Usman Nasir, Hamid Olimjon, Gafur Ghulam, Erkin Vahidov, Abdulla Oripov. Humanity should be embedded in human blood. In this place, I.A. Karimov said: "Love for the country, the feeling of humanitarianism is an age-old feature embedded in the blood of our people. The issue of preserving and further improving these unique ancient qualities and educating our children as worthy sons and daughters of a free and democratic Uzbekistan should be the main direction of our work in the field of spirituality," he said. is appropriate. Every person can be a true patriot only when he has his own homeland. Humaneness, honoring the country, place, and people where one was born and raised, caring about its economic, social, political, cultural, and spiritual development, giving development its due to make a contribution, to burn his soul to preserve the independence of his country, and if necessary, to dedicate his life to it.

Humanism is caring for all people living on the mother earth, regardless of their nationality, religion, social status. Humanity is the unity of a person's good thoughts and good deeds. Humanism is a factor that leads to spiritual growth in society, a characteristic that gives beauty to our national spirituality, national spirit, traditions, and values. a concept that expresses concern about creating the conditions for release. The humanitarian idea of education is an important concept in which the destiny of a person or person lies. The idea of humanitarianism is an eternal and universal value of every nation. At the center of education is the individual, it is undoubtedly important to form the ideas of humanity and goodness in children of preschool age, in the future life, socialization, and career choice of the child.

Another characteristic of humanity is intelligence. Man is considered superior to other creatures only with his mind. In some books, the highest human feelings: love, loyalty and justice are glorified as the highest quality of humanity. However, the difference between man and other creatures is in the mind. Other creatures have such higher feelings as we do. For example, loyalty in a dog and loyalty in a horse can also be found in humans. In the works of our great scholars such as Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mirza Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, the ideas of humanity, human freedom, and his dignity were promoted. Farobi tried to prove that friendly and friendly living of people in the country would bring great benefits to the peoples, and he strongly encouraged peace and focused all his activities on the service of people. Navoi made caring for the destiny of man, the interests of the people, and the country the main issue. He put forward the idea that the most valuable thing in the world is a person. In his opinion, the whole being should serve man and his happiness. World religions, including Islam, embody the ideas of humanitarianism. In it, it is encouraged to help the poor, the poor, the foreigner, the needy, and to be generous and honest. This indicates that the ideas of humanity and goodness in our country are passed down from generation to generation as an eternal heritage. Even the mother's alla for a newborn baby includes the concepts of humanity and kindness. From this point of view, humanitarianism defines the country's way of life. Inculcating these noble ideas in the young generation, especially children of preschool age, is an important issue today.

As we know, the main activity of preschool children is play. The game is one of the skills that children of preschool age can acquire. It is an activity that encourages to learn, to further increase love for people and nature, and to learn human qualities such as responding to good with

good. Humane education is a process of formation of human qualities of a person that gives a person the opportunity to feel morally, socially, politically and legally effective and protected. Nowadays, one of the important problems of education is the shallowing of the idea of humanity. On this issue, a number of programs have been developed in pre-school educational organizations and all educational institutions, and these programs should be fully compatible with today's culture. E.Kh. Shiyonov, one of the famous pedagogic scientists of the world, studied the idea of humanity in young children and came to the following conclusion: "The development of the individual in harmony with the universal culture and goodness determines the development of the basic social culture." From this point of view, we are forming the basis of universal human qualities and collective culture of the near future in preschool education organizations. This, in turn, requires all pedagogues - workers, educators to approach their profession responsibly.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. His speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the topic "Rule of law and ensuring human interests - a guarantee of the country's development and people's well-being". - T.: "Uzbekistan", 2017. - 48 p.
2. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rules of every leader's activity. - T.: "Uzbekistan". - 2017. - 102b.
3. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. - T.: "Uzbekistan", 2017. - 488 p.
4. Sadiqova Sh.A. Preschool pedagogy T.: Tafakkur bostoni 2013
5. N.M. Egamberdiyeva Social pedagogy.- T.:2014 Textbook
6. O.U. Khasanboyeva et al. Family pedagogy. Tashkent, "Fan and technologies" publishing house. 2007 year.
7. M. Kayumova. Preschool pedagogy.- T.: 2018 Textbook
8. Bobomurodov A. Islamic manners and culture. T. "Cholpon". 1995.
9. "Uzbekistan" 1994 on the road to independence and development
10. Shodmonova Sh. Pedagogy of preschool education. Tashkent, "Science and Technology" publishing house. 2008.